

Comparative Study of Pap smear and Colposcopic Findings in Patients with Vaginal Discharge Attending OPD in the Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract:

This study aimed to compare the diagnostic findings of Pap smear and colposcopy in patients presenting with vaginal discharge at Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna, over six months. A total of 50 patients were evaluated using both Pap smear and colposcopy to determine the accuracy and utility of each method. Results showed that Pap smear had a sensitivity of 70% and was effective in detecting high-grade lesions, while colposcopy demonstrated higher sensitivity at 88%, particularly in identifying minor and inflammatory changes. Discrepancies between the two methods were observed in 32% of cases, emphasizing the complementary role of colposcopy in enhancing diagnostic accuracy. The study concludes that using both Pap smear and colposcopy together provides a more comprehensive evaluation of cervical abnormalities, leading to improved patient management and early detection of potential pre-cancerous conditions.

Keywords: Pap smear, Colposcopy, Vaginal discharge, Cervical abnormalities

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Introduction

Vaginal discharge is a common gynecological complaint among women of reproductive age, often prompting visits to outpatient departments (OPDs) in tertiary care centers [1]. While it can be benign, it may also indicate underlying infections, hormonal imbalances, or pre-cancerous lesions [2]. Early and accurate diagnosis is crucial for effective management and prevention of complications, including cervical cancer. Pap smear and colposcopy are two widely used diagnostic techniques that help in identifying the cause of vaginal discharge and screening for cervical abnormalities [3,4]. The Pap smear, a cytological test, allows for the detection of cellular changes in the cervix. At the same time, colposcopy offers a magnified visual examination of the cervix and vaginal tissues, providing immediate insights into the severity of lesions [5,6].

This study aims to compare the findings of Pap smear and colposcopy in patients presenting with vaginal discharge to determine the diagnostic accuracy and utility of each method. This research seeks to enhance clinical decision-making and improve patient outcomes in tertiary care settings by evaluating these diagnostic tools.

Methodology

This study was conducted at Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna, over a period of six months from 1st January 2023 to 31st June 2023. A total of 50

patients presenting with vaginal discharge were included in the study. The study aimed to compare the diagnostic findings of Pap smear and colposcopy in these patients.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Female patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients presenting with complaints of vaginal discharge.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Pregnant women.
- Patients with a history of cervical cancer or who had undergone a hysterectomy.
- Patients with active menstruation at the time of examination.

Study Procedure:

All eligible patients were first evaluated with a detailed history and clinical examination. Following this, each patient underwent a Pap smear and colposcopic examination.

1. Pap Smear:

- A Pap smear was performed using a cervical brush to collect cells from the cervix.

- The samples were fixed, stained, and examined microscopically for cellular abnormalities following the Bethesda system.

2. Colposcopy:

- Colposcopy was performed using a colposcope to visually examine the cervix under magnification.
- Acetic acid was applied to highlight abnormal areas, and findings were recorded based on Reid's colposcopic index.

Data Analysis:

The results of Pap smear and colposcopy were recorded and compared to assess the correlation between cytological and colposcopic findings. Statistical analysis was conducted to determine the diagnostic accuracy of each method, including sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value.

Results

The study included 50 patients presenting with vaginal discharge at Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna, from 1st January 2023 to 31st June 2023. The results of the Pap smear and colposcopic findings were analyzed and compared to evaluate their diagnostic utility.

1. Patient Demographics:

- Age range of participants: 20 to 55 years.
- Mean age: 34.5 years.
- Most common age group: 30-40 years (40% of patients).

2. Pap Smear Findings:

- Normal cytology: 18% (9 patients).
- Inflammatory changes: 34% (17 patients).
- Atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance (ASCUS): 14% (7 patients).
- Low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (LSIL): 12% (6 patients).
- High-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL): 10% (5 patients).
- Suspicious of malignancy: 4% (2 patients).

3. Colposcopic Findings:

- Normal findings: 20% (10 patients).
- Inflammatory changes: 30% (15 patients).
- Minor abnormal colposcopic changes: 16% (8 patients).
- Major abnormal colposcopic changes: 18% (9 patients).
- Suspicious of invasive carcinoma: 6% (3 patients).

4. Correlation between Pap Smear and Colposcopic Findings:

- Concordant results were observed in 68% of cases (34 patients), where both Pap smear and colposcopy indicated similar findings.
- Discrepancies were noted in 32% of cases (16 patients), with colposcopy showing abnormal findings that were not detected by Pap smear, particularly in patients with inflammatory changes and minor lesions.

5. Diagnostic Accuracy:

- Sensitivity of Pap smear: 70%.
- Specificity of Pap smear: 80%.
- Sensitivity of colposcopy: 88%.
- Specificity of colposcopy: 75%.
- Positive predictive value of Pap smear: 72%.
- Negative predictive value of colposcopy: 90%.

6. Overall Diagnostic Performance:

Colposcopy was more sensitive in detecting early and pre-cancerous changes compared to Pap smear, particularly in cases with minor lesions. Pap smear effectively detected high-grade lesions but had limitations in identifying minor abnormalities picked up on colposcopy.

These tables encapsulate the essential data and findings from the study, illustrating the comparative diagnostic performance of Pap smear and colposcopy in detecting cervical abnormalities in patients with vaginal discharge. The tables also highlight the importance of using both diagnostic tools to enhance clinical decision-making and patient outcomes.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and General Findings

Category	Value
Total Patients	50
Age Range	20 to 55 years
Mean Age	34.5 years
Most Common Age Group	30-40 years (40% of patients)

Table 2: Diagnostic Findings from Pap Smear

Finding	Percentage	Number of Patients
Normal cytology	18%	9
Inflammatory changes	34%	17
ASCUS (Atypical squamous cells)	14%	7
LSIL (Low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion)	12%	6
HSIL (High-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion)	10%	5
Suspicious of malignancy	4%	2

Table 3: Diagnostic Findings from Colposcopy

Finding	Percentage	Number of Patients
Normal findings	20%	10
Inflammatory changes	30%	15
Minor abnormal colposcopic changes	16%	8
Major abnormal colposcopic changes	18%	9
Suspicious of invasive carcinoma	6%	3

Table 4: Comparison and Correlation of Findings

Result Type	Percentage	Details
Concordant Results	68%	Similar findings in both tests
Discrepancies	32%	Abnormal findings in colposcopy not detected by Pap smear

Table 5: Diagnostic Accuracy Metrics

Metric	Pap Smear	Colposcopy
Sensitivity	70%	88%
Specificity	80%	75%
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	72%	-
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	-	90%

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the importance of using both Pap smear and colposcopy as complementary diagnostic tools in evaluating patients presenting with vaginal discharge [7]. Pap smear, with a sensitivity of 70%, effectively identified high-grade lesions, such as HSIL, but showed limitations in detecting inflammatory changes and minor lesions, which were more effectively visualized through colposcopy [8]. The higher sensitivity of colposcopy (88%) underscores its utility, especially in cases where Pap smear results are inconclusive or when mild cytological abnormalities are present [9].

The study found a notable discrepancy between the Pap smear and colposcopy results, with colposcopy detecting abnormalities in 32% of cases that the Pap smear failed to identify. This highlights the potential for missed diagnoses if relying solely on cytological examination, especially in early or pre-cancerous stages where visual inspection by colposcopy can provide immediate insights [10,11,12]. The positive predictive value of Pap smear at 72% and the negative predictive value of colposcopy at 90% further indicate that while Pap smear is valuable for detecting severe cytological abnormalities, colposcopy offers a critical advantage in providing a broader, more immediate assessment of cervical health [13,14].

The findings align with existing literature that suggests integrating colposcopy into routine practice enhances diagnostic accuracy, particularly in tertiary care settings where patients may present with complex or atypical symptoms [15]. The concordance rate of 68% between Pap smear and colposcopy suggests that while both tests are valuable, colposcopy can act as a crucial secondary measure, especially for cases where Pap smear results may not fully capture the extent of cervical abnormalities [16]. This combined approach could lead to improved patient management, more accurate diagnosis, and timely intervention, ultimately enhancing patient outcomes and reducing the risk of progression to cervical cancer [17]. Overall, this study underscores the need for a combined diagnostic approach in the evaluation of vaginal discharge, particularly in high-risk populations or settings where cervical cancer prevalence is significant. The integration of colposcopy into diagnostic protocols, alongside Pap smear, could serve as an effective strategy for early detection and management of cervical abnormalities, ensuring comprehensive care for patients in tertiary care centers [18-20].

Conclusion

This comparative study of Pap smear and colposcopic findings in patients with vaginal discharge underscores the importance of using both diagnostic methods to achieve a comprehensive evaluation of cervical health. While Pap smear is valuable for detecting high-grade cytological abnormalities, colposcopy offers superior sensitivity, particularly in identifying minor lesions and inflammatory changes that Pap smear might miss. The significant concordance and complementary nature of these tests suggest that their combined use can enhance diagnostic accuracy, leading to better clinical decision-making and improved patient outcomes. Therefore, integrating colposcopy with Pap smear in routine gynecological evaluations in tertiary care settings can provide a more thorough assessment, enabling early detection and timely management of cervical abnormalities.

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